

FORMATION AND COURSE OF ALCOHOLISM IN YOUNG WOMEN WITH ALCOHOLIC PSYCHOSIS

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ABSTRACT

In recent decades, the number of women suffering from alcoholism has been increasing in many economically developed countries of the world. According to various authors, at present the number of women with alcohol dependence continues to increase, but the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of the disease process in women registered with drug addiction have not been studied enough, despite the available publications.

On the basis of the Samarkand Regional Narcological Dispensary, for the purpose of the experiment, assistance is being provided in the restoration and overcoming of alcohol dependence in young women who have undergone alcoholic psychosis. The study sample consisted of 32 patients hospitalized for alcoholic psychosis in the Samarkand Regional Narcological Dispensary. Results. The vast majority of women start drinking alcohol quite late (at 18-20 years of age), and the onset of systematic alcoholization in them is noted after a long period of time and occurs at the age of 26 years and older. The first stage of alcoholism in most of the women studied lasted more than 4 years, but did not exceed 7 years, and the duration of the second stage was not marked by a long duration and often was up to 3 years. In most cases, alcoholic psychoses in women developed 6–10 years after the formation of alcohol dependence. A large percentage of hereditary burden for drug addiction and mental illness was noted among the examined women. Conclusions. In connection with the fairly rapid formation and course of female alcoholism, it is necessary to carry out timely prevention of alcoholism in young women, using a set of social and medical measures.

INTRODUCTION. According to statistics, in recent decades, the number of women suffering from alcoholism has been growing in Russia, as well as in many economically developed countries [3, 22]. In some of them, the number of women who abuse alcohol is increasing much faster than the number of men who abuse alcohol. The ratio of alcoholized women and men fluctuates in a wide range. Thus, in the Soviet Union, the ratio of alcoholic women and men varied from 1:9.8 to 1:12.6 [7, 24]. According to the latest published data [5, 27], in 2013 the ratio of alcoholic women to men is 1:3, i.e. the number of women suffering from alcoholism is constantly and steadily growing.

The rate of formation of alcoholism in women is the subject of heated discussion between experts [2, 4]. Most researchers note the accelerated development of alcoholism in young women, unlike men. This fact is much more common in the works of researchers based on the examination of patients hospitalized in inpatient departments [6, 15, 18], and is less often discussed when studying patients on an outpatient basis [1, 23].

A number of works are devoted to the development of alcoholism in women [9, 26]. It has been shown that when alcoholism occurs in young women, alcoholic disease develops malignantly [8, 25] and corresponds to the development of alcoholism in men [10, 13].

According to various authors, at present the number of women with alcohol dependence continues to grow [11, 16, 21]. Existing state forms of registration of narcological patients contain a limited number of indicators for a detailed analysis of this contingent. Socio-demographic and

clinical characteristics of the disease process in women registered with drug addiction have not been studied enough, despite the available publications [12, 14, 19]. In connection with the above, the relevance of the study is assessed as quite high.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY: conducted at the Samarkand Regional Narcological Dispensary, was to help young women with alcoholic psychosis recover and get rid of addiction.

DISCUSSION AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Young women who entered the Samarkand Regional Narcological Dispensary from 2019 to 2021 were selected for the study. The study sample included 32 patients hospitalized for alcoholic psychosis.

The inclusion criteria for the study were:

- 1) age of patients from 25 to 44 years;
- 2) an established diagnosis of mental and behavioral disorders due to alcohol use, addiction syndrome, stage II;
- 3) an established diagnosis of alcoholic psychosis (acute alcoholic delirium, acute alcoholic hallucinosis).

In the course of the work, the following research methods were used: clinical-psychopathological, clinical-dynamic, statistical. Processing of the results of the study was carried out by the methods of multivariate statistics, correlation analysis; the reliability of the obtained data was assessed using the Mann-Whitney u-test (for non-uniform samples) and Student's t-test (for uniform samples in exceptional cases).

The study was conducted by interviewing patients, their relatives, examining patients, filling out statistical cards of patients. Working in a hospital, one of the authors of the article in most cases personally took part in the hospitalization

of patients and their subsequent treatment, observed the clinical dynamics of the course of alcoholic psychosis and the patients' recovery from it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The study group included 32 patients, the average age of which was $37,22 \pm 5,6$ years, with the second stage of alcoholism, who are on inpatient treatment for alcoholic psychoses.

All subjects were divided into 4 groups according to age (25-30 years old, 31-35 years old, 36-40 years old, 41-44 years old). The largest number of female patients with alcoholic psychosis examined was 31-35 years old (34,4%) and 41-44 years old (25,0%). A smaller number of patients were in the age groups of 25-30 year olds (21,88%) and 36-40 year olds (18,72%).

In 21,88% of the studied heredity was not burdened by alcoholism, drug addiction or mental illness. The presence of burdened heredity on the father's side was noted in 25,0% of patients, on the mother's side - in 9,4%. In 12,5% of patients, heredity was burdened by distant relatives (cousins, grandfather or grandmother, etc.), from brothers or sisters - in 6,25%. In 3,1% of the studied heredity was aggravated by

mental illness of the next of kin, and in 25,0% of patients there was no information about hereditary burden for drug addiction and mental illness.

The studied contingent had the following nosological forms of alcoholic psychoses. Diagnoses in the examined groups were formulated according to the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision "Mental and behavioral disorders caused by alcohol use, withdrawal syndrome with delirium: delirium classic, typical (F10.402), delirium with convulsive seizures (F10.412), abortive delirium (F10.452), acute alcoholic hallucinosis or psychotic disorder, predominantly hallucinatory (F10.522), structurally complex psychosis or psychotic disorder, predominantly polymorphic (F10.532).

Thus, we have obtained the following general nosological structure of alcoholic psychoses in the examined persons.

The predominant number of patients (57,1%) was diagnosed with "Alcoholic delirium" (Table 1). Acute alcoholic hallucinosis was 2,3 times less common (24,6%) in the examined patients. Structural-complex alcoholic psychosis was diagnosed in 18,3% of patients.

table 1

Clinical and nosological forms of alcoholic psychoses by groups of subjects

Nosological form	Women (n=32)	
	abs	%
Alcoholic delirium	17	53,1
Acute alcoholic hallucinosis	8	25,0
Structural-complex	7	21,9

psychosis

Thus, delirium tremens was the most common form of alcoholic psychosis in the subjects. The number of patients with acute alcoholic hallucinosis only slightly prevailed over the number of patients with structurally complex psychosis.

The study revealed that out of 32 patients, the vast majority (81,25%) began to drink alcohol even before the age of majority, 18,75% of patients began to drink alcohol at the age of 18-20, and only 3,1% after 20 years.

The age of onset of systematic alcoholization in patients also varied within different age limits. Systematic alcoholization means drinking 200-300 ml (maximum 500 ml) of vodka 1-2 times a week.

A larger number of women (40,6%) began to systematically consume alcohol at the age of 21-25, 31,25% at the age of 18-20. The smallest number of patients (18,75% and 9,4%) began to resort to taking alcoholic beverages at the age of 26-30 and at 31 and older, respectively.

In more than half of the examined women (50,0%), the first stage of alcoholism was characterized by a duration of 4-5 years. 2,2 times less often (25,0%) in women, the duration of the first stage of alcoholism

was 6-7 years. In the smallest number of women (17,1% and 7,9%), the duration of the first stage was up to 3 and 8-9 years, respectively. The second stage of alcoholism most often (37,5%) in women lasted up to 5 years. In a slightly smaller number of patients (28,1% and 18,75%), the duration of the second stage of alcoholism was up to 3 and up to 10 years, respectively. Only in a minimal proportion of the subjects (9,4%) the second stage lasted more than 10 years.

In the majority of the subjects (40,6%), the alcohol withdrawal syndrome formed soon after the onset of alcoholization at the age of 21-25 years. About a third of women (30,1%) noted the onset of a hangover syndrome at the age of 26-30 years. With a rarer frequency, withdrawal syndrome was formed after 31 years (21,9%) and at 18-20 years (7,4%).

The duration of the course of alcoholism before the onset of the first psychosis is up to 10 years or more. More than half of alcoholic psychoses (50,0%) are observed among the subjects who become alcoholic for 6-10 years. In 30,1% of patients, the first alcoholic psychosis was noted with a duration of alcoholism of more than 10 years and in 19,9% - up to 5 years.

Data on the age distribution of patients with the manifestation of the first alcoholic psychosis are presented in Table 2

table 2

Age of patients at the manifestation of the first alcoholic psychosis

Age of patients, years	Women (n=32)	
	abs	%
25-30 лет	13	40,6

31-35 лет	8	25,0
36-40 лет	6	18,8
41-44 года	5	15,6

Most of the first manifesting alcoholic psychoses occur at the age of 25-30 years (40,6%). The first alcoholic psychosis occurred 1,6 times less frequently (25,0%) at the age of 31-35 years and 2,2 times less frequently (18,8%) in the age group of 36-40 years. The smallest number (15,6%) of first manifesting alcoholic psychoses in our study was noted at the age of 41-44 years.

CONCLUSION: From the foregoing, it follows that the formation and course of alcohol dependence in young women who have undergone alcoholic psychosis have certain characteristics. Thus, the majority of women begin to drink alcohol quite late (at the age of 18–20 years), and the onset of systematic alcoholization is noted in them after a long period of time and occurs at the age of 26 years and older. In our study, it was noted that the first stage of alcoholism in most of the women studied

lasted more than 4 years, but did not exceed 7 years, and the duration of the second stage was not characterized by a long duration and often was up to 3 years.

In the course of the study, it was noted that in women, in most cases, alcoholic psychoses developed after 6-10 years from the onset of the formation of alcohol dependence. Also, among the examined women, a large percentage of hereditary burden for drug addiction and mental illness was recorded.

Thus, in the course of the study, the features of the formation and course of alcoholic disease in women were revealed, which substantiates the scientific novelty of the work and its relevance in the current situation of growing alcoholism and the increased frequency of alcoholic psychosis in young women.

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